

Cluster-Wise Hyperparameter Optimization Enhances Regional Rainfall–Runoff Modeling with Deep Learning: A Robust CAMELS-US Benchmark

Farzad Hosseini ^{a,*}, Cristina Prieto^a, Cesar Alvarez^a

^aInstituto de Hidráulica Ambiental de la Universidad de Cantabria (IHCantabria), 39011 Santander, Cantabria, Spain

Abstract

This study presents a highly optimized deep-learning benchmark for rainfall–runoff modelling on 531 CAMELS-US basins. Using the same basin set and train/validation/test split adopted in an established regional benchmark, we combined large-scale random-search hyperparameter optimization, ensemble deep learning, and a cluster-wise validation-based selection strategy to construct a stronger and more informative regionally trained Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) benchmark. Candidate models were trained in a fully regional multi-basin setting and then selected either as top-performing regional configurations or through cluster-wise validation ranking within hydrologically coherent basin groups. The resulting frameworks were evaluated over the fixed test period using whole-hydrograph, water-year, and seasonal diagnostics.

Optimized ensemble frameworks improved upon the reference benchmark, with the cluster-wise selected regional ensemble delivering the strongest over-

*Corresponding author.

Email address: farzad.hosseini@alumnos.unican.es (Farzad Hosseini)

all performance. Over the full test hydrograph, it achieved median NSE = 0.82 and mean NSE = 0.78, while reducing RMSE, peak-magnitude error, and missed-peaks ratio relative to the reference. These improvements were maintained across both water-year and seasonal evaluations. Performance, however, was not spatially or temporally uniform. Skill was highest in wetter, more runoff-efficient basins and in basins with stronger snow-related seasonal runoff signals, where the runoff response tends to be more organized and learnable. Skill was weakest in drier, more water-limited basins with frequent low-flow or near-zero-flow conditions and more intermittent runoff responses, where the forcing–response relation is less stable and more difficult to predict.

Keywords: Regional modelling, Rainfall–runoff modelling, Ensemble deep learning, Hydrologic regimes, CAMELS-US, Large-sample hydrology

1. Introduction

Accurate rainfall–runoff simulation underpins a wide range of hydrologic science and practice, from water-resources planning and drought management to flood forecasting and infrastructure design. Across these applications, the central challenge is to learn (or encode) nonlinear catchment responses to meteorological forcings while remaining robust across diverse climates, physiographies, and hydrologic regimes (Beven (2020); Prieto et al. (2020)). Historically, this has been addressed with conceptual and process-based models, often calibrated basin-by-basin (Prieto et al. (2021, 2022)); however, calibration can be data- and expertise-intensive, and model structures may not generalize uniformly across regions (Refsgaard et al. (2022)).

The emergence of large-sample hydrology datasets has shifted the landscape by enabling systematic cross-basin learning and benchmarking. In particular, CAMELS-US provides decades of daily meteorological forcings, discharge observations, and extensive static catchment attributes for hundreds of minimally impacted basins, and has become a de facto testbed for regional rainfall–runoff modeling (Addor et al. (2017)).

1.1. Deep learning for rainfall–runoff modeling in the CAMELS-US era

Over roughly the last decade, deep learning (DL) (Goodfellow et al. (2016))—and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997)) in particular—has become one of the strongest and most widely used data-driven approaches for rainfall–runoff modelling (Kratzert et al. (2019); Beven (2020); Shen and Lawson (2021); Xie et al. (2021); Tripathy and Mishra (2024); Donnelly et al. (2024); Hosseini et al. (2025b)). Early influential work demonstrated that LSTM networks can learn runoff dynamics directly from meteorological inputs at levels competitive with established conceptual benchmarks (Kratzert et al., 2018). Shortly thereafter, large-sample training across hundreds of basins showed that a single regional LSTM can outperform many traditional models and can implicitly learn hydrologically meaningful patterns, while variants such as entity-aware LSTMs incorporate static attributes to tailor behavior to each basin (Kratzert et al., 2024; Heudorfer et al., 2025). Recent work has rapidly expanded the space of deep-learning approaches in hydrology, including broader benchmarking efforts, alternative architectures, and generalization studies in space and time (e.g., Tripathy and Mishra, 2024). In parallel, attention-based models and Transformers have been proposed for rainfall–runoff modeling and related hy-

drologic prediction tasks, with ongoing efforts to benchmark RNNs against attention-based architectures under unified evaluation frameworks (Liu et al., 2024). To date, however, these studies have generally reported performance
40 that is comparable to, rather than clearly better than, strong recurrent benchmark models, including the well-established regional benchmark of Kratzert et al. (2024).

Despite this progress, CAMELS-US benchmarking studies still face a persistent practical barrier: *the lack of a highly optimized, transparent, and*
45 *reusable deep-learning benchmark evaluated under a standardized and comprehensive protocol.* Many papers compare new architectures against a limited set of baselines, often with heterogeneous data splits, varying input configurations, and (crucially) insufficient or uneven hyperparameter tuning across methods. This can blur the interpretation of reported gains: improvements
50 may reflect tuning effort as much as model innovation. Recent community discussion has emphasized that evaluation practices and experimental design choices (e.g., single-basin vs. multi-basin training) can substantially affect conclusions and that carefully standardized protocols are needed for fair comparison and reproducibility (Kratzert et al., 2024; Hosseini et al., 2025a). At
55 the same time, work on human vs. metric-based assessment suggests that while hydrologists value visual judgment, commonly used quantitative metrics broadly align with expert preferences when applied consistently, reinforcing the value of transparent metric-driven benchmarks that are comparable between studies (Gauch et al., 2023).

60 1.2. *Why a new benchmark is needed*

Three issues motivate presenting a new benchmark for CAMELS-US rainfall–runoff deep learning modeling.

(1) **Optimization matters for conclusions.** Modern DL hydrology models have many interacting hyperparameters (e.g., hidden size, dropout, learning rate schedules, input sequence length, regularization, and optimization settings). Without thorough hyperparameter optimization (HPO), reported results may under-represent what a model class can achieve (Hosseini et al., 2024a). Conversely, new methods can outperform primarily because they receive more tuning attention than the existing baselines. A benchmark intended to support method development should therefore report results from 70 *highly optimized* models under a fixed, reproducible HPO protocol.

(2) **Accuracy across hydrologic regimes and temporal variability matters.** Benchmarking only on aggregate hydrograph metrics can mask systematic weaknesses across hydrologic regimes, seasons, and water 75 years. A benchmark that supports hydrologically meaningful comparative research should therefore evaluate not only overall skill but also performance across seasonal regimes and interannual variability, with attention to regime-dependent behavior.

(3) **Protocol completeness is essential for comparative hydrology.** To be useful to the wider community, a benchmark should provide: 80 (i) a fixed train/validation/test split that is already recognized and used in the literature; (ii) a fine-grained diagnostic evaluation of test-period predictions across all CAMELS-US basins that goes beyond whole-hydrograph and median-based summaries, thereby allowing regional performance to be as-

85 sessed without obscuring hydrologic heterogeneity or the uniqueness of place
(Beven, 2020); (iii) clearly defined metrics and strict evaluation rules; and
(iv) open code so future work can be compared *without re-implementing*
pipelines.

1.3. Contributions of this study

90 In this work, we address these gaps by presenting a new, highly opti-
mized deep learning LSTM benchmark for rainfall–runoff modeling on 531
catchments from CAMELS-US. Our experimental protocol follows the same
basin set and train/validation/test splitting strategy as Kratzert et al. (2024),
enabling direct and fair comparability with the existing CAMELS-US DL hy-
95 drology baselines and practices discussed in that reference. We then extend
the state of the art by combining large-scale HPO and ensemble learning with
a *cluster-wise regionalization* strategy designed in this research to increase
accuracy while preserving generalization.

Our main aims are:

- 100 **1. Presenting a highly optimized regional LSTM benchmark on
CAMELS-US (531 basins) for comparative hydrology.** We
conduct systematic, large-scale hyperparameter optimization for deep-
learning rainfall–runoff models over a 10-dimensional search space with
648,000 possible combinations, and evaluate the resulting benchmark
105 across all 531 CAMELS-US basins, including cluster-wise diagnostic
analyses.
- 2. Introducing a cluster-wise validation-based selection strategy
for regional LSTM ensembles.** Beyond a single nationwide regional

model, we introduce a framework in which basins are grouped by hydro-
110 logic similarity and optimized regional models are selected per cluster
based on validation performance. This selection strategy accounts for
regime-dependent validation behavior while retaining the benefits of
multi-basin regional training. We build ensembles from top-performing
115 configurations identified during 2000-trial regional random-search HPO
to improve reliability and reduce sensitivity to initialization and opti-
mization, producing a strong and stable reference model class for future
comparisons. The search was computationally intensive, requiring more
than six months of parallel GPU-accelerated training on the Neptune
supercomputing cluster, with each training job using two NVIDIA A30
120 GPUs, 8 CPU cores, and 16 GB RAM per CPU.

3. **An extensive evaluation protocol for regional rainfall–runoff
models.** We provide a comprehensive evaluation that goes beyond ag-
gregate median scores by analyzing (i) basin-wise performance across
the full CAMELS-US sample, (ii) spatial and hydrologic contrasts in
125 model behavior across clusters and individual basins, so that regional
skill can be assessed without obscuring hydrologic heterogeneity or the
uniqueness of place, (iii) variability across water years, and (iv) seasonal
performance patterns. This protocol is intended as a reusable template
for comparative hydrology studies. It also supports hydrologic diag-
130 nostic interpretation of where regional LSTMs perform strongly and
where their remaining limitations are concentrated, helping to identify
regimes that deserve further methodological and process-oriented in-
vestigation. We emphasize that this is a diagnostic hydrologic analysis

rather than a formal explainable-AI study.

135 **4. Open code and reusable benchmark artifacts.** We release code, model configurations, and benchmark outputs, including test-period runoff predictions for all 531 basins, to enable researchers to compare new regional modelling approaches against a transparent, high-accuracy regional deep-learning baseline under a consistent protocol.

140 **2. Materials and methods**

2.1. Study area and dataset (CAMELS-US)

This study uses the 531 minimally impacted CONUS catchments from CAMELS-US, following the same basin set adopted by Kratzert et al. (2024). CAMELS-US provides a large-sample hydrologic benchmark that combines
145 daily meteorological forcings, observed discharge, and a broad set of static catchment attributes describing climate, topography, soils, geology, and land cover (Addor et al., 2017). This setting is particularly suitable for regional rainfall–runoff modelling because it exposes models to a wide range of hydro-climatic conditions within a consistent observational framework.

150 Across the 531 basins, the study sample spans broad hydro-climatic gradients in catchment size, elevation, aridity, snow influence, and flow regime. To describe these gradients, Table 1 summarizes the main catchment attributes using distributional statistics. Together, these summaries show that the benchmark covers broad climatic and physiographic contrasts as well
155 as markedly different runoff-generation, storage-related, and flow-variability behaviours.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the 531 CAMELS-US basins grouped into six hydrologically informed clusters across the conterminous United States.

To reduce hydro-climatic heterogeneity while preserving the advantages of regional training, the 531 basins were organized into six clusters, which form the basis of the cluster-wise regional modelling framework (see Section 2.6). Their spatial distribution is shown in Figure 1, while their hydro-climatic characteristics are summarized in Table 2. Although several clusters are geographically coherent, the grouping is not merely spatial; rather, it also reflects distinct hydrologic signatures, as shown in Figure 2. This supports the idea that regional models can exploit meaningful hydro-climatic similarities across basins, consistent with the multi-basin training perspective of Kratzert et al. (2024).

The six clusters display clear contrasts in both climate and hydrologic response. Cluster 1 is characterized by comparatively large basins, low slopes, low runoff ratios, low baseflow indices, and frequent low-flow conditions.

Table 1: Distributional summary of selected climatic, physiographic, and hydrologic attributes for the 531 CAMELS-US basins used in this study. Q5 and Q95 denote the 5th and 95th percentiles, respectively.

Attribute	Unit	Q5	Mean	Median	Q95
Catchment area	km ²	23.26	494.99	337.19	1581.39
Mean elevation	m	64.24	737.05	437.01	2656.98
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	1.54	3.41	3.27	6.49
Aridity index	–	0.34	0.98	0.85	2.03
Snow fraction	–	0.002	0.172	0.090	0.675
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.12	1.61	1.17	5.48
Runoff ratio	–	0.08	0.41	0.36	0.90
Baseflow index	–	0.18	0.49	0.50	0.72
Flow-duration-curve slope	–	0.34	1.26	1.30	2.01
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	1.45	23.48	15.20	65.43
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.70	106.37	97.15	254.14
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.13

170 Cluster 2 forms the largest and most moderate cluster, with intermediate hydro-climatic conditions and comparatively stable storage-related behavior. Cluster 3 represents the driest and most water-limited regime, with the lowest precipitation (1.83 mm d⁻¹), lowest discharge (0.21 mm d⁻¹), lowest runoff ratio (0.11), highest aridity (1.75), and highest low-flow frequency (212.4), consistent with strongly moisture-limited behavior. Cluster 175 4 is the wettest and most runoff-efficient cluster, with the highest median precipitation (6.29 mm d⁻¹), discharge (5.36 mm d⁻¹), runoff ratio (0.78),

Table 2: Hydro-climatic summary of the six CAMELS-US clusters used in the cluster-wise regional modelling framework. Reported values are cluster medians.

Cluster	n	P	Aridity	Snow frac.	Q	Runoff ratio	BFI	Low-flow freq.
1	83	2.77	0.90	0.08	0.79	0.28	0.31	179.20
2	195	3.50	0.73	0.10	1.48	0.42	0.51	75.25
3	67	1.83	1.75	0.02	0.21	0.11	0.35	212.40
4	61	6.29	0.36	0.14	5.36	0.78	0.55	96.85
5	66	2.41	1.38	0.66	1.23	0.53	0.61	76.05
6	59	3.68	0.87	0.00	1.05	0.30	0.49	85.15

P : mean precipitation [mm d⁻¹]; Snow frac.: fraction of precipitation falling as snow; Q : mean discharge [mm d⁻¹]; BFI: baseflow index; Low-flow freq.: low-flow frequency.

Aridity is defined as the ratio of potential evapotranspiration to precipitation, following the CAMELS-US attribute definition.

and flow-duration-curve slope (1.80), indicating steep and responsive flow regimes. Cluster 5 is the most snow-influenced and topographically elevated cluster, with the highest snow fraction (0.66) and mean elevation (2483.86 m),
 180 whereas Cluster 6 is distinguished by low-elevation basins with limited snow influence and intermediate hydrologic efficiency.

The hydro-climatic contrasts summarized in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Table 2 define a set of clearly different runoff regimes against which regional
 185 deep learning models can be evaluated. Thus, the benchmark is not limited to aggregate CONUS-wide performance, but is rooted in a structured hydro-climatic domain that enables later analysis of where model performance is strong and where limitations remain concentrated. This is particularly relevant in the present study, where the cluster-wise LSTM framework is intended

Hydrological signatures across the six clusters

Figure 2: Distribution of key hydrological signatures across the six clusters, highlighting contrasts in runoff efficiency, storage-related behavior, flow variability, and discharge regime.

190 not only to improve predictive accuracy, but also to provide a more hydrologically interpretable basis for analyzing learned behavior across distinct rainfall–runoff regimes.

Additional climatic, physiographic, and regionalization details are provided in the Supplementary Materials (Figures S1–S3 and Tables S1–S3).

195 2.2. Inputs, targets, and preprocessing

For each basin, the model inputs consist of daily meteorological forcings (denoted x_t) and static catchment attributes, and the target variable is daily discharge (denoted q_t) at the outlet of each catchment. We follow the standard preprocessing pipeline used in the benchmarking reference

Figure 3: Hydro-climatic profile of the six clusters. Cell values show raw cluster medians, whereas colors represent standardized anomalies relative to the across-cluster median structure.

200 (Kratzert et al., 2024): (i) time series are aligned per basin, (ii) missing values are handled according to the established dataset conventions and the benchmark-consistent preprocessing procedures implemented in the Neural-Hydrology framework. Recent work by Gauch et al. (2025) has explicitly addressed the question of how to handle missing input data in hydrologic

205 deep-learning systems, further emphasizing that preprocessing choices should remain benchmark-consistent and operationally robust. Dynamic inputs are then normalized using statistics computed on the training period to avoid information leakage. Discharge is modelled in a strictly out-of-sample manner, and all reported results correspond to the fixed test period described below.

210 2.3. Data splitting protocol

To ensure strict comparability with established deep-learning benchmarks on CAMELS-US, we adopt the same training/validation/test split as Kratzert et al. (2024). This split is not intended to represent an operational forecasting

setup, but rather to provide a standardized evaluation protocol that enables
215 direct comparison with existing benchmark results. Specifically, we use:

- **Training:** 1 Oct 1999 – 30 Sep 2008
- **Validation:** 1 Oct 1980 – 30 Sep 1989
- **Testing:** 1 Oct 1989 – 30 Sep 1999

All model-selection decisions, including hyperparameter choice and ensemble
220 membership, are based exclusively on validation performance. The released
benchmark consists of runoff predictions over the fixed test period for all
531 CAMELS-US basins. Future comparative studies can therefore evaluate
their models on the same test period, for either the full benchmark or any
subset of basins, and directly compare predictions and metrics against our
225 released outputs. Note that all benchmark models are trained in a regional
multi-basin setting, i.e., using data from all 531 catchments. Consistent
with prior work (Kratzert et al., 2024; Hosseini et al., 2025a), such regional
training typically improves generalization and predictive performance relative
to single-basin or cluster-restricted training, because exposure to a larger
230 and more diverse set of catchments helps the model learn more transferable
hydrologic relationships.

2.4. Model class: regional LSTM networks

We model the rainfall–runoff relationship using Long Short-Term Mem-
ory (LSTM) networks, which have become a strong baseline for large-sample
235 hydrology (Kratzert et al., 2018; Beven, 2020; Shen and Lawson, 2021; Tri-
pathy and Mishra, 2024). Let $\mathbf{x}_{t-L+1:t}$ denote the input sequence of length

L . The LSTM produces hidden states \mathbf{h}_t that are mapped to discharge via a feed-forward head:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \text{LSTM}(\mathbf{x}_{t-L+1:t}; \theta), \quad \hat{q}_t = f(\mathbf{h}_t; \phi). \quad (1)$$

In contrast to a single fixed architecture, we evaluate an ensemble-ready
240 family of regional LSTM configurations, varying sequence length, hidden size, dropout, number of layers, and optimization settings. Strong configurations are then selected through systematic hyperparameter optimization.

2.5. Hyperparameter optimization via random search

We perform hyperparameter optimization using the random-search strat-
245 egy for deep-learning rainfall-runoff models described by Hosseini et al. (2024a,b). Random search is particularly suitable for high-dimensional configuration spaces typical in deep-learning models and provides a reproducible mechanism to explore interacting hyperparameters efficiently (Bergstra and Bengio (2012)).

250 For each candidate configuration $c \in \mathcal{C}$ sampled from the predefined search space, we train the corresponding LSTM on the **training** period and evaluate its performance on the **validation** period. In total, the random search explored 2000 regional LSTM configurations, all trained using data from the full set of 531 basins. We use a composite validation objective
255 that combines Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) and Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE). Specifically, configurations are ranked based on basin-wise NSE and KGE values computed over the validation period, using both mean and median aggregation across basins to promote robustness, consistent with the robustness-oriented selection philosophy in Hosseini et al. (2025a).

260 *Hyperparameter search space.* The hyperparameter optimization (HPO) design was constructed to explore the main architectural and training choices expected to influence regional LSTM performance while remaining computationally feasible at the CONUS scale. Rather than relying on a single pre-defined regional configuration, we performed large-scale random search over
265 key model and training hyperparameters and then selected high-performing configurations for two purposes: (i) identifying the strongest overall regional model family (Top-10) and (ii) constructing the final cluster-wise regional ensemble framework. Table 3 summarizes four complementary views of the setup: the full HPO search space used in this study, the subset of values
270 represented among the selected Top-10 regional configurations, the subset represented among the selected cluster-wise configurations, and the fixed benchmark regional configuration adopted from the reference setup. This comparison clarifies not only the breadth of the search space, but also which regions of that space were retained among the strongest final models.

275 For full reproducibility, we release the exact configuration files defining all search ranges, sampling choices, benchmark settings, and selected model setups together with the code.

2.6. Cluster-wise validation-based regional model selection

We adopt the same hydrologic clustering strategy introduced by Kratzert
280 et al. (2024) to partition the 531 CAMELS-US basins into six groups with similar catchment characteristics. Briefly, basins are clustered using k -means ($k = 6$) on 25 static catchment attributes spanning climate, vegetation, soils, geology, and topography. The number of clusters was selected based on silhouette analysis, yielding six clusters. These clusters define the cluster-

Table 3: Hyperparameter search space explored in this study, the values represented among the selected Top-10 regional configurations, the values represented among the selected cluster-wise configurations, and the fixed regional benchmark configuration adopted from the reference setup.

Hyperparameter	Full HPO search space	Selected Top-10 regional family	Selected cluster-wise family	Regional benchmark (Kratzert et al., 2024)
Sequence length L [days]	90, 120, 180, 270, 365, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1095, 1460, 1825	90, 365, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1460	270, 365, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1460, 1825	365
Hidden size	16, 32, 64, 128, 256	64, 128, 256	128, 256	256
Initial forget-gate bias	-3, -1, 0, 1, 3, 5	-3, -1, 1, 3, 5	-3, -1, 0, 1, 3, 5	3
Output dropout	0, 0.2, 0.4	0, 0.2, 0.4	0, 0.2, 0.4	0.4
Batch size	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	256
Learning rate at epoch 0 (Lr0)	10^{-3} , 10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}
Learning rate at epoch 10 (Lr10)	5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3} , 5×10^{-3}	5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	5×10^{-4}
Learning rate at epoch 25 (Lr25)	10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	10^{-4}
Target-noise standard deviation	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1	0
Loss function	NSE, RMSE	NSE, RMSE	NSE, RMSE	NSE
Number of retained configurations		10 regional configs	18 configs (top 3 per cluster)	single fixed setup

285 wise evaluation and model-selection units used in this study, with each basin assigned to exactly one cluster. Thus, “cluster-wise” refers to validation-based selection and diagnostic evaluation, not to cluster-restricted training.

A central contribution of this paper is the introduction of the **cluster-wise** strategy for constructing a high-accuracy deep learning benchmark that 290 reduces regime heterogeneity while preserving the benefits of regional multi-basin training. During hyperparameter optimization (HPO), candidate models are not trained separately for each basin or each cluster. Instead, all candidate configurations are trained in a regional setting using data from all 531 basins. Each trained candidate is then evaluated separately within 295 each cluster using only the basins belonging to that cluster, and the top-performing regional configurations are identified for each cluster based on validation performance.

More specifically, for each cluster $k \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$, we: (i) run random-search HPO over N_{RS} sampled configurations using the full 531-basin training 300 set; (ii) score each configuration according to its validation performance over the basins belonging to cluster k ; and (iii) select the top three configurations for that cluster. The final benchmark is then constructed as a cluster-wise regional ensemble framework, in which the three best regional configurations associated with each cluster are used to generate test-period predictions for 305 all 531 catchments.

For clarity, the term *cluster-wise* in our methodology refers to post-HPO model selection based on cluster-specific validation performance, and does not involve training separate models per cluster. All candidate models are trained in a fully regional multi-basin setting using data from all 531

310 basins. In this way, all searched regional configurations are assessed across
the six clusters, and the final ensemble is built by selecting the strongest
regional models within each cluster. Notably, the configurations selected as
top-performing for individual clusters were also among the strongest con-
figurations overall when regional performance was aggregated using median
315 evaluation metrics.

2.7. Ensemble deep learning over optimized models and final benchmark model

To improve reliability and reduce sensitivity to training stochasticity, we
adopt ensemble deep learning principles from Hosseini et al. (2025a, 2024b).
After completing HPO, we perform a *cluster-wise* post-hyperparameter op-
320 timization (post-HPO) configuration selection focusing on the six hydrologic
clusters of Kratzert et al. (2024): for each cluster $k \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ we rank
all HPO configurations by their validation performance computed only over
basins belonging to cluster k , and select the top three configurations. This
yields a set of $6 \times 3 = 18$ regionally trained model configurations whose
325 inclusion in the final ensemble is determined by cluster-specific validation
performance.

All candidate models in post-HPO stage are retrained in a fully regional
(multi-basin) setting using data from all 531 CAMELS-US basins. At this
step, we retrain each of the 18 selected configurations using $S = 10$ random
330 seeds. To control overfitting, model training was monitored on the valida-
tion set, and the optimal training epoch was selected based on validation
performance. TensorBoard logs were used to inspect training and validation
trajectories during this process. For a given seed s , this produces an en-
semble of 18 members, whose predictions are aggregated at each time step

335 using the median operator. Unless otherwise stated, basin-wise benchmark metrics are computed from the seed-averaged prediction series, while seed-level diagnostics are reported separately in the Supplementary Materials. This follows the “wisdom of crowds” rationale (Surowiecki, 2004) in a technical ensemble-learning sense: aggregating multiple independently retrained, 340 high-performing LSTM configurations can reduce sensitivity to individual model realizations and occasional outlying predictions. We therefore use the median operator as a robust aggregation rule, consistent with the ensemble strategy presented by Hosseini et al. (2025a). The resulting system produces $S = 10$ final prediction series per basin (one per seed), which we release as 345 part of the benchmark. For each of the 531 basins, the final prediction for a given seed is obtained by aggregating all 18 selected regional configurations, not only the three configurations associated with the basin’s own cluster.

Let $\hat{q}_t^{(k,i,s)}$ denote the discharge prediction at time t from the model corresponding to cluster $k \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$, within-cluster rank $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, and 350 random seed $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$ with $S = 10$. For each seed s , the ensemble prediction is:

$$\hat{q}_t^{(s)} = \text{median}\left(\{\hat{q}_t^{(k,i,s)}\}_{k=1}^6 \prod_{i=1}^3\right), \quad (2)$$

and the released benchmark consists of the set of prediction series $\{\hat{q}_t^{(s)}\}_{s=1}^S$ for each of the 531 basins over the fixed test period. This design enables direct comparison with the reference benchmark of Kratzert et al. (2024).

355 *Proposed benchmark.* The resulting system defines the **proposed cluster-wise selected regional LSTM ensemble benchmark** for CAMELS-US. In this proposed benchmark, test-period discharge in each basin is predicted by an ensemble of regionally trained, highly optimized LSTMs whose mem-

bership is selected through cluster-wise validation ranking across the six hydrologic clusters. Results are reported consistently for all 531 basins under the fixed test period, enabling direct comparison with the reference benchmark of Kratzert et al. (2024). This design leverages the “wisdom of crowds” principle by combining complementary regional models selected from different cluster-specific validation rankings, while using median aggregation to improve robustness against individual model variability.

2.8. Evaluation protocol: overall, seasonal, inter-annual, and basin-wise distribution performance

Beyond overall test-period skill following the reference protocol of Kratzert et al. (2024), we propose an extensive evaluation protocol intended for **comparative regional hydrology**. The protocol combines established practices from our prior ensemble work (Hosseini et al., 2025a) with new diagnostic perspectives to characterize when and where regional deep-learning models perform strongly and where their limitations remain concentrated. A central motivation is that whole-hydrograph and aggregate summary scores alone are not sufficient to characterize regional benchmark behavior across a hydro-climatically diverse basin sample such as CAMELS-US.

2.8.1. Primary performance metrics

We compute a suite of hydrologically standard performance metrics for each basin over the fixed test period, including Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970), Kling–Gupta efficiency (KGE) (Gupta et al., 2009), Pearson correlation, RMSE, peak-timing error, peak-magnitude error (Peak-MAPE), and the missed-peaks ratio. Detailed definitions of these

metrics and their implementation are provided in Supplementary Material 2
of Hosseini et al. (2025b). Results are analyzed through basin-wise distribu-
385 tions, spatial diagnostics, and cross-basin summary statistics, with particular
emphasis on robust summaries such as the median and interquartile range.

2.8.2. *Water-year evaluation (inter-annual robustness)*

To quantify inter-annual variability, we compute metrics separately for
each **water year** (WY; Oct–Sep) in the test period. For each basin b and
390 water year y , we compute $NSE_{b,y}$. We then analyze how basin-wise per-
formance distributions change across water years, summarize cluster-wise
temporal differences that reveal regime-dependent weaknesses, and use sup-
plementary diagnostics to identify the hydrologic conditions associated with
comparatively weaker or stronger years.

395 2.8.3. *Seasonal evaluation*

To evaluate model performance across different parts of the annual cycle,
we compute performance separately for four fixed three-month seasons: JFM,
AMJ, JAS, and OND. For each basin b and season s , we compute $NSE_{b,s}$
and summarize the results across basins and clusters. This reveals whether
400 improvements are concentrated in specific calendar seasons or sustained more
consistently throughout the annual cycle.

2.8.4. *Basin-wise distribution performance and hydrologic heterogeneity*

A key component of the proposed protocol is the explicit analysis of
basin-wise performance distributions. Rather than relying only on a
405 single nationwide summary statistic, the protocol is designed to support a
finer-grained evaluation of how performance is distributed across the full

basin population and across hydrologically coherent clusters, which is examined in detail in the Discussion. This is important because regional benchmark skill should be assessed without obscuring hydrologic heterogeneity or the uniqueness of place, as emphasized by Beven (2020). Basin-wise distributions help reveal whether gains are broadly shared across the domain, concentrated in particular hydrologic regimes, or offset by lower-skill tails in specific subsets of basins. They also provide the diagnostic basis for interpreting spatial patterns of success and failure in comparative hydrology.

2.8.5. Comparative benchmark outputs

To support reproducibility and direct method comparison, we release: (i) basin-wise predictions on the fixed test period for all 531 basins, (ii) the full evaluation scripts implementing the protocol above, and (iii) all code and configuration metadata necessary to reproduce the benchmark and extend it with new regional modelling ideas.

3. Results

3.1. Overall benchmark performance

We begin by comparing the three benchmark frameworks over the full test-period hydrograph: the reference regional benchmark of Kratzert et al. (2024), the proposed Top-10 regional ensemble, and the proposed cluster-wise selected regional ensemble. First, we report both median and mean statistics across the 531 CAMELS-US basins. The median is retained as the primary robust summary, while the mean provides complementary information on aggregate regional performance.

430 Table 4 shows that both proposed ensemble frameworks outperform the
reference benchmark in most key metrics. Relative to the benchmark, both
the Top-10 and cluster-wise ensembles achieve higher median NSE, lower
RMSE, lower peak-timing error, lower Peak-MAPE, and lower missed-peaks
ratio. Importantly, these improvements are not limited to the medians. Mean
435 NSE also improves from 0.75 for the reference benchmark to 0.77 for the Top-
10 family and 0.78 for the cluster-wise family, indicating that the gain extends
beyond the central tendency and is reflected at the level of aggregate regional
performance. From this perspective, the proposed benchmark is stronger not
only for the typical basin but also across the broader 531-basin sample.

440 Among the two proposed frameworks, the cluster-wise selected regional
ensemble provides the strongest overall performance profile across most full-
hydrograph metrics. At the full-hydrograph scale, KGE remains broadly
comparable among the benchmark frameworks, whereas the clearest aggregate
improvements are observed in NSE, correlation, RMSE, peak-magnitude
445 error, and missed-peaks ratio. It attains the highest median NSE (0.82), the
highest mean NSE (0.78), the highest median Pearson correlation (0.92),
and the lowest Peak-MAPE (34.36) and missed-peaks ratio (0.33) among
the three frameworks. The Top-10 family also clearly improves upon the
reference benchmark and remains close to the cluster-wise family, but with
450 slightly weaker overall aggregate performance.

Figure 4 places the tabulated results in a basin-wise distributional con-
text. The boxplots show a clear rightward shift in NSE for both proposed
frameworks relative to the benchmark, confirming that the improvement is
not confined to a small subset of basins. The cluster-wise family yields the

Table 4: Comparison of the three benchmark frameworks over the full test-period hydrograph. For each framework, both the median and mean across the 531 basins are reported. The median is shown as the primary robust summary, while the mean is included to reflect aggregate regional performance across the full basin population.

Framework	Summary	NSE	KGE	Pearson- r	RMSE	Peak time	Peak-MAPE	Missed peaks
Benchmark (Kratzert et al., 2024)	Median	0.79	0.79	0.90	1.13	0.27	35.22	0.35
	Mean	0.75	0.74	0.88	1.32	0.39	38.45	0.38
Top-10 family ensemble	Median	0.81	0.77	0.91	1.06	0.24	34.86	0.33
	Mean	0.77	0.73	0.90	1.25	0.37	37.53	0.37
Cluster-wise family ensemble	Median	0.82	0.79	0.92	1.06	0.25	34.36	0.33
	Mean	0.78	0.74	0.90	1.25	0.36	37.21	0.36

* Bold values indicate the best result in each column within each summary type (higher values are better for NSE, KGE, and Pearson- r , whereas lower values are better for RMSE, peak time, Peak-MAPE, and missed peaks). RMSE is reported in mm d^{-1} . Peak time is reported in days. Peak-MAPE is reported in %. Missed peaks denotes the fraction of observed peaks that were not satisfactorily captured under the adopted peak-evaluation procedure.

455 highest central tendency and the highest upper-quartile behavior, while the Top-10 family remains close. This result is important because it demonstrates that the proposed methodology does not simply improve a few isolated cases, but strengthens the distribution of basin-level outcomes across the benchmark domain.

460 Figure 5 further clarifies where the gains occur by separating the basin population into a lower-skill subset ($\text{NSE} < 0.5$) and a higher-skill subset ($\text{NSE} \geq 0.5$), defined here for diagnostic purposes. In the lower-skill subset, both proposed frameworks reduce the number of poorly performing basins

Figure 4: Distribution of basin-wise NSE values across the 531 CAMELS-US basins, computed from test-period predictions after averaging across seeds for each framework. Both proposed frameworks shift the performance distribution toward higher NSE relative to the reference benchmark, with the cluster-wise family achieving the strongest overall distribution.

from 33 to 30. In the higher-skill subset, the empirical distributions show
 465 a systematic rightward improvement relative to the benchmark. Together,
 these patterns indicate that the proposed frameworks improve both the cen-
 tral part of the basin-performance distribution and the lower-performing tail.
 This provides strong support for treating the new ensembles as improved
 regional benchmarks rather than merely tuned alternatives with gains re-
 470 stricted to a narrow subset of basins.

Additional seed-level robustness diagnostics are provided in the Supple-
 mentary Materials, where both proposed frameworks also show stable behav-

Figure 5: ECDF of basin-wise NSE across the 531 CAMELS-US basins, computed from seed-averaged predictions and split into lower-skill ($NSE < 0.5$) and higher-skill ($NSE \geq 0.5$) subsets, defined here for diagnostic purposes. Both proposed frameworks reduce the number of lower-performing basins relative to the benchmark and improve the NSE distribution across the larger higher-skill subset.

ior across repeated random-seed realizations. These supplementary analyses support the interpretation that the observed gains are not driven by a single
 475 favorable initialization, but reflect a consistent advantage of the optimized ensemble frameworks.

Taken together, Table 4 and Figures 4–5 establish a clear first result of the study: both proposed optimized ensemble frameworks outperform the reference benchmark, and the cluster-wise family emerges as the strongest
 480 overall benchmark candidate. Having established this improvement relative to the existing benchmark, the remaining analyses focus primarily on the internal behavior of the two proposed frameworks, with particular emphasis on the comparison between the cluster-wise and Top-10 families across different

temporal and hydrologic evaluation settings.

485 *3.2. Temporal robustness across water years*

When evaluation is restricted to water-year slices, performance decreases moderately relative to the whole-hydrograph case, but remains broadly robust. Relative to the full-hydrograph evaluation, the reference benchmark declines from a median NSE of 0.792 to 0.766, while median KGE decreases
490 from 0.789 to 0.722. Nevertheless, the two proposed frameworks remain clearly stronger under the same year-by-year evaluation: the cluster-wise family reaches a median NSE of 0.792 and the Top-10 family a median NSE of 0.793, compared with 0.766 for the reference benchmark. A similar pattern is observed for KGE and Pearson correlation, with median KGE values
495 of 0.733 and 0.728 for the cluster-wise and Top-10 families, respectively, and median Pearson correlations of 0.919 and 0.917, both above the benchmark value of 0.907. This indicates that the gain of the optimized ensemble frameworks is not lost when the test period is disaggregated into shorter and more hydrologically variable temporal units.

500 To make the inter-annual comparison explicit, Table 5 reports the exact yearly median basin-wise NSE values for the three frameworks. Two points are immediately evident. First, both proposed frameworks outperform the reference benchmark in every single water year considered. Second, the cluster-wise family is the strongest performer in most years, ranking first
505 in 8 out of 10 water years, while the Top-10 family ranks first in the remaining two years (1993 and 1996) by a very narrow margin. The mean over water years confirms the same ordering, with values of 0.788 for the benchmark, 0.817 for the cluster-wise family, and 0.813 for the Top-10 family. Thus, the

outperformance of the proposed frameworks is temporally persistent rather
 510 than being driven by only a small subset of favorable years.

Table 5: Median basin-wise NSE by water year for the three benchmark frameworks, computed from seed-averaged predictions. Bold values indicate the best-performing framework in each water year. The last two rows summarize the average yearly performance and the number of years in which each framework ranks first.

Water year	Benchmark	Cluster-wise	Top-10
1990	0.768	0.789	0.786
1991	0.784	0.808	0.802
1992	0.757	0.804	0.789
1993	0.804	0.827	0.828
1994	0.790	0.822	0.818
1995	0.793	0.826	0.821
1996	0.764	0.788	0.790
1997	0.810	0.838	0.832
1998	0.826	0.850	0.847
1999	0.785	0.818	0.816
Mean over water years	0.788	0.817	0.813
Years ranked first	0	8	2

The same temporal structure is visualized in Figure 6, which shows the year-by-year evolution of median basin-wise NSE together with the interquartile range across basins. The two proposed frameworks remain consistently above the reference benchmark in all water years. The separation is not

Figure 6: Water-year evolution of median basin-wise NSE across the 531 CAMELS-US basins, computed from seed-averaged predictions. Shaded bands denote the interquartile range across basins. Both proposed frameworks remain consistently above the reference benchmark across all test years.

515 large in every year, but it is systematic, which is particularly important for regional benchmarking. The cluster-wise family is generally the strongest performer, while the Top-10 family remains very close and follows nearly the same temporal trajectory. This suggests that the main gain comes from the optimization method and the proposed ensemble framework itself, with the

520 cluster-wise selection strategy providing an additional but more moderate advantage.

This pattern is summarized more compactly in Figure 7, where the year-by-model matrix of median basin-wise NSE highlights the same persistent inter-annual ordering. Because the heatmap uses an adaptive color scale

525 differences become visually interpretable rather than being compressed into

Heatmap of median basin-wise NSE by water year and benchmark framework

Figure 7: Heatmap of median basin-wise NSE by water year and benchmark framework. The adaptive color scaling reveals the persistent inter-annual advantage of the two proposed frameworks over the reference benchmark and shows that the cluster-wise family is most frequently the strongest performer.

a nearly uniform color field. The figure shows that the reference benchmark occupies a systematically lower performance band in every water year, whereas the two proposed frameworks remain in a higher performance range throughout. Consistent with Table 5, the cluster-wise family is most often the best-performing option, although the Top-10 family remains highly competitive and slightly leads in a small number of years. The Top-10 family also has a lower computational cost at the retained-configuration stage, as it uses 10 configurations compared with 18 in the cluster-wise ensemble.

535 To examine the distribution of basin-level
 level outcomes within each water year,
 Figure 8 stacks the yearly boxplots
 of basin-wise NSE for the three bench-
 mark frameworks. These panels show
 540 that the reference benchmark remains
 more vulnerable to lower-performing
 tails in several water years, whereas
 both proposed frameworks shift the
 yearly basin distributions upward while
 545 preserving a broadly similar interquar-
 tile structure. This is important be-
 cause it indicates that the improve-
 ment is not driven solely by a small
 subset of exceptionally well-predicted
 550 basins; rather, the gain reflects a
 broader upward displacement of basin-
 wise performance across time.

Yearly distributions of basin-wise NSE

Figure 8: Yearly distributions of basin-wise NSE for the cluster-wise family ensemble, Top-10 family ensemble, and reference benchmark.

An additional observation is that the three LSTM-based frameworks preserve a similar inter-annual ordering of stronger and weaker water years. While this does not by itself demonstrate similar internal representations, it suggests that these recurrent models respond to a common hydrologic difficulty structure in the test period. This may indicate that some aspects of inter-annual predictability are controlled more by the hydroclimatic character of the years than by architectural variation within the LSTM family.

Overall, the water-year analysis confirms that the performance gains of the proposed frameworks are temporally robust. The advantage over the reference benchmark persists from year to year rather than arising from a particular aggregation effect over the full hydrograph. Among the two developed alternatives, the cluster-wise family again emerges as the most consistently strong option, although the close behavior of the cluster-wise and Top-10 families suggests that the principal gain comes from the optimized ensemble framework itself, with the cluster-wise strategy adding a further but more moderate improvement. Detailed seed-level water-year robustness diagnostics are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

3.3. Seasonal performance

Seasonal evaluation reveals a clear regime dependence in benchmark performance. Across all three frameworks, AMJ is the strongest season, whereas JAS is consistently the most challenging. This seasonal contrast is already visible in the reference benchmark diagnostics: AMJ yields the highest benchmark median NSE (0.635), KGE (0.655), and Pearson correlation (0.900), while JAS shows the weakest benchmark behavior, with median NSE close to zero (-0.006), median KGE = 0.353, the largest peak-magnitude error

(Peak-MAPE = 48.763%), and the highest missed-peaks ratio (0.393). JFM also performs relatively well, whereas OND occupies an intermediate position
580 between the wet-season and dry-season extremes.

From the perspective of comparative benchmarking, however, the most important result is that this seasonal structure is improved systematically by the proposed optimized ensemble frameworks. Table 6 shows that both developed frameworks outperform the reference benchmark in every season when
585 seasonal NSE is summarized consistently across water years. The cluster-wise family is the strongest performer in all four seasons, with median seasonal NSE values of 0.745 (JFM), 0.761 (AMJ), 0.494 (JAS), and 0.644 (OND), compared with 0.685, 0.696, 0.368, and 0.565 for the benchmark, respectively. The Top-10 family remains very close, but slightly below the cluster-wise
590 family in all seasons.

Two conclusions follow from these results. First, the proposed benchmark improvement is not season-specific: it persists from winter to autumn and therefore reflects a broader strengthening of regional model behavior rather than a gain restricted to only one regime. Second, the relative gain is
595 especially important in the more difficult seasons. In absolute terms, JAS remains the hardest period for all frameworks, but the cluster-wise family still raises seasonal median NSE from 0.368 to 0.494, while OND improves from 0.565 to 0.644. These gains are meaningful because they indicate that the optimized framework does not only reinforce performance in already easier
600 regimes such as AMJ, but also alleviates part of the benchmark weakness in more challenging seasonal conditions.

The seasonal behavior of the strongest framework is visualized in Fig-

Table 6: Seasonal median NSE summarized across water years for the three benchmark frameworks. Bold values indicate the best-performing framework within each season. The final column reports the mean of the four seasonal summaries for each framework.

Framework	JFM	AMJ	JAS	OND	Overall
Benchmark	0.685	0.696	0.368	0.565	0.579
Top-10 family	0.737	0.751	0.488	0.634	0.652
Cluster-wise family	0.745	0.761	0.494	0.644	0.661

Values are based on seasonal NSE summaries aggregated across water years. JFM: January–March; AMJ: April–June; JAS: July–September; OND: October–December.

ure 9 for the cluster-wise family. The same seasonal ordering is also observed for the other two frameworks. The figure confirms that the seasonal hierarchy remains stable through time: AMJ is consistently the strongest season, JFM is also robust, JAS remains the weakest regime across nearly all water years, and OND occupies an intermediate position. At the same time, the heatmap shows that even within this stable seasonal ordering, there is meaningful inter-annual variability, which helps explain why seasonal aggregation is informative for benchmark interpretation.

Overall, the seasonal analysis shows that the proposed benchmark improvement is both systematic and hydrologically meaningful. The optimized frameworks improve performance in all seasons, while the cluster-wise family emerges as the strongest option throughout. At the same time, the persistently weaker performance in JAS indicates that warm-season runoff prediction remains an important benchmark challenge for future rainfall–runoff modelling research.

Seasonal heatmap of median basin-wise NSE across water years for the cluster-wise family benchmark

Figure 9: Seasonal heatmap of median basin-wise NSE across water years for the cluster-wise family. The figure shows a stable seasonal ordering, with AMJ generally providing the strongest performance, JFM also remaining robust, JAS being the most challenging season, and OND occupying an intermediate position.

4. Discussion

4.1. Benchmark skill is strong, but hydrologically structured rather than spatially uniform

620

A central result of this benchmark is that predictive skill is not distributed randomly across the CAMELS-US domain, but instead follows a clear hydrologic-geographic structure. In the study-area analysis, the six clusters were shown to differ systematically in climatic forcing, runoff efficiency, snow influence, storage-related behavior, and flow variability. The interpretation of model performance is therefore grounded in a hydrologic

625

classification that was defined independently of the benchmark results themselves. When basin-wise performance is aggregated over these six hydrologically coherent clusters, a stable ordering emerges across the benchmark frameworks: Clusters 4 and 5 are consistently the most favorable groups, Cluster 3 is clearly the most difficult, and Clusters 1, 2, and 6 occupy intermediate positions. This ordering is visible not only in median NSE, but also in mean, minimum, and maximum NSE, indicating that the spatial structure of skill is robust to the choice of summary statistic. In other words, the benchmark does not merely perform well “on average”; it performs differently across distinct runoff regimes, and those differences appear systematic rather than incidental.

This type of regime-dependent behavior is exactly why large-sample comparative hydrology is useful. As emphasized by Addor et al. (2017), individual basins can be viewed as occupying a continuum of climatic, physiographic, and hydrologic gradients, and broad-sample analyses make it possible to interpret performance changes along those gradients rather than only in isolated sites. The present benchmark is consistent with that perspective: it suggests that the deep-learning models are not only fitting a continental data set in a generic sense, but exhibit systematically different performance across basin classes with distinct runoff-generation characteristics. This is also in line with the broader regional deep-learning view that multi-basin LSTM models can exploit common information across catchments while still showing regime-dependent strengths and weaknesses (Kratzert et al., 2024).

The cluster-wise family, which is the strongest overall framework in this study, provides the clearest picture of this hydrologic geography of perfor-

Figure 10: Cluster-level summary of basin-wise NSE for the three benchmark frameworks. The four panels report the median, mean, minimum, and maximum NSE across basins within each hydrologically coherent cluster, after averaging predictions over seeds for each basin. Each panel uses its own adaptive color scale to improve visual discrimination of between-cluster differences.

mance. Its median NSE is highest in Cluster 4 (0.881) and Cluster 5 (0.872), followed by Cluster 2 (0.818), Cluster 6 (0.775), and Cluster 1 (0.761), while Cluster 3 is distinctly weaker (0.684). The same ranking is almost preserved
 655 in the mean NSE, indicating that the cluster ordering is not driven only by a few unusually good or bad basins. The lower-bound behavior is even more

Table 7: Cluster-wise family ensemble: cluster-level summary of basin-wise NSE. Reported values are computed across basins within each hydrologically coherent cluster after seed-averaging at basin level.

Statistic	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
Median	0.761	0.818	0.684	0.881	0.872	0.775
Mean	0.732	0.801	0.598	0.879	0.857	0.760
Q25	0.591	0.696	0.464	0.834	0.819	0.636
Q75	0.888	0.923	0.826	0.923	0.931	0.858
Minimum	0.170	0.398	-0.346	0.765	0.417	0.518
Maximum	0.913	0.918	0.891	0.960	0.963	0.903

revealing: Cluster 4 has a minimum NSE of 0.765, meaning that even its more difficult basins remain well predicted, while Cluster 3 drops to -0.346 , showing that this group contains the strongest local performance limitations in the benchmark. Thus, the main between-cluster contrast is not only about central tendency, but also about robustness. Some clusters are not only easier on average; they are also less prone to severe local underperformance. This distinction matters because good aggregate metrics do not necessarily imply equally credible hydrologic behavior across all basins, and similar summary skill can still hide important differences in within-group stability or process adequacy (Refsgaard et al., 2022; Beven, 2020).

The overall benchmark is also strong in absolute terms. Only 30 out of 531 basins fall below $NSE = 0.5$, corresponding to about 5.65% of the benchmark sample, while 300 basins ($\sim 56.5\%$) achieve $NSE \geq 0.8$, and 53

Table 8: Summary of performance-defined benchmark subsets for the cluster-wise family. The $NSE < 0.5$ subset is used as a diagnostic threshold subset in the discussion, not as a categorical claim about model adequacy.

Subset definition	Number of basins	Share of benchmark (%)
$NSE < 0.5$	30	5.65
$NSE \geq 0.6$	478	90.02
$NSE \geq 0.7$	437	82.30
$NSE \geq 0.8$	300	56.50
$NSE \geq 0.9$	53	9.98

670 basins ($\sim 10\%$) achieve $NSE \geq 0.9$. Thus, the main scientific question is not whether the benchmark works in a broad sense, but rather where, why, and under which hydrologic conditions its remaining failures occur. That question is precisely where a continental benchmark becomes most informative.

675 *4.2. Favorable and difficult regimes: runoff efficiency, intermittency, and snow influence*

The strong performance in Clusters 4 and 5 is hydrologically plausible and consistent with the cluster descriptors reported earlier in the manuscript. Cluster 4 is the wettest and most runoff-efficient group in the study sample, with the highest precipitation, discharge, runoff ratio, and flow-duration-curve slope, indicating steep and responsive rainfall–runoff behavior. Cluster 5, although not as wet as Cluster 4, is the most snow-influenced and topographically elevated group. Its runoff timing may therefore be more strongly organized by seasonal accumulation and melt dynamics, which can impose

a relatively coherent annual structure on streamflow. In both cases, the hydroclimatic signal presented to the model appears more structured than in
685 the drier and more intermittent parts of the domain. The benchmark therefore suggests that strong predictive skill is favored in regimes where runoff generation is either efficient and responsive, or seasonally well organized.

The updated diagnostics reinforce this interpretation. Basins with $NSE \geq$
690 0.8 and especially those with $NSE \geq 0.9$ are disproportionately concentrated in Clusters 4 and 5, whereas Cluster 3 contains no basin with $NSE \geq 0.9$. The high-skill subsets are characterized by higher precipitation, higher mean discharge, higher runoff ratio, higher snow fraction, higher elevation, and lower zero-flow tendency than the lower-skill subset. This pattern suggests
695 that the most predictable basins in the present benchmark are not simply the wettest in a trivial sense, but the ones in which streamflow is supported by a relatively clear and persistent seasonal runoff structure, higher runoff efficiency, and clearer forcing–response behavior.

The snow-influenced basins are particularly noteworthy. The current re-
700 sults do not indicate that snow-dominated or snow-influenced basins are among the dominant failure regimes. If anything, the opposite pattern emerges: snowier and higher-elevation basins are disproportionately represented among the high-skill subsets, whereas the lower-skill subset is characterized much more by aridity, low runoff efficiency, and intermittent or zero-
705 dominated flow behavior. A cautious interpretation is that snow-influenced basins tend to exhibit a more structured and temporally organized runoff signal, which is more consistently captured by the model under the present benchmark setting. This should not be over-interpreted as evidence that the

model fully captures snow processes in a process-consistent sense; rather, it
710 suggests that, within this benchmark, snow-influenced regimes may provide
a more organized hydroclimatic signal than the drier and more threshold-
dominated regimes where most failures are concentrated.

By contrast, Cluster 3 is the most hydrologically challenging group for
all three frameworks, and this is also consistent with its hydroclimatic signa-
715 ture. In the study-area description, Cluster 3 is the driest and most water-
limited cluster, with the lowest precipitation, lowest discharge, lowest runoff
ratio, highest aridity, and highest low-flow frequency. The new diagnostic re-
sults sharpen that picture: the lower-skill subset is characterized by very low
runoff ratio, very low mean flow, high low-flow frequency, high zero-flow ten-
720 dency, high precipitation-zero frequency, and elevated flow variability. These
properties suggest that runoff generation in this group is more likely to be
thresholded, episodic, and highly sensitive to small errors in forcing or an-
tecedent state. In such basins, precipitation may often fail to generate appre-
ciable runoff, while under particular preconditions relatively modest inputs
725 can trigger disproportionate response. This kind of intermittency is inher-
ently harder to learn from standard daily forcing–response data, especially
when the controlling factors include storage state, subsurface pathways, and
local geological effects that are only indirectly represented in the available
predictors.

730 The intermediate behavior of Clusters 1, 2, and 6 also fits their hydro-
logic context. Cluster 2 is the largest and most moderate group, with com-
paratively stable storage-related behavior; its relatively strong and stable
performance suggests that moderate hydro-climatic regimes are favorable for

regional LSTM learning. Cluster 6 also performs reasonably well, with a comparatively strong lower bound, which may indicate that despite its limited snow influence, its runoff generation remains sufficiently organized and not excessively dominated by intermittent low-flow behavior. Cluster 1 is more ambiguous: it shows a respectable median NSE, but a noticeably weaker minimum and mean relative to its median. Hydrologically, this is consistent with a group containing larger basins, lower slopes, lower runoff ratios, lower baseflow indices, and frequent low-flow conditions. In such settings, catchment response may be more heterogeneous, more routing-influenced, and less directly tied to local daily forcings, making some basins in the group materially harder than the cluster median alone would suggest.

4.3. *The lower-skill subset, uniqueness of place, and the limits of data-only explanations*

Perhaps the most revealing result is not that some clusters are easier than others, but that the remaining benchmark limitations are concentrated in a relatively small subset of basins. Only 30 out of 531 basins fall below the diagnostic threshold of $NSE < 0.5$, and only one basin yields a negative NSE. Moreover, these 30 lower-skill basins are not evenly spread across the domain; they are concentrated mainly in Cluster 3, with smaller contributions from Clusters 1 and 2 and only an isolated case in Cluster 5. This concentration is especially noticeable because it occurs primarily in the same cluster that was previously identified as the driest, most water-limited, and most low-flow-prone regime in the study domain. The result therefore suggests that the benchmark is not limited by a broad structural inability to model CAMELS-US basins, but rather by a relatively small set of hydrologically difficult or

Table 9: Cluster-wise distribution of lower-skill basins using two diagnostic thresholds in the cluster-wise family benchmark. Percentages are relative to the number of basins in each cluster.

Cluster	n basins	n with $NSE < 0.5$	Share (%)	n with $NSE < 0.7$	Share (%)
C1	83	6	7.2	22	26.5
C2	195	2	1.0	20	10.3
C3	67	21	31.3	36	53.7
C4	61	0	0.0	0	0.0
C5	66	1	1.5	2	3.0
C6	59	0	0.0	14	23.7

locally anomalous cases.

760 The geographic figures reinforce this interpretation. The lower-skill basins are not simply isolated at the continental scale in a random sense; rather, they appear embedded in spatially coherent hydro-climatic settings. Figure 11 makes this especially clear by separating the 30 weakest basins from the rest of the CAMELS-US population, while Figure 12 places these failures into the
765 broader spatial structure of cluster-wise benchmark skill. Together, the two figures suggest that the residual failures are associated with combinations of climate, topography, storage behavior, and likely geology that are organized in space. This does not prove that geography itself is the cause, but it strongly supports the interpretation that the difficult basins are not arbitrary
770 statistical outliers. That is exactly the kind of spatially organized anomaly that comparative hydrology is designed to expose (Addor et al., 2017).

Figure 11: Geographic distribution of the lower-skill basins in the cluster-wise family benchmark. The 30 basins with $NSE < 0.5$ are highlighted and colored by their seed-averaged NSE values, while the remaining 501 CAMELS-US basins are shown in gray. The figure shows that the weakest basins are not randomly scattered across CONUS, but are concentrated in a limited set of hydro-climatic settings, especially within the more water-limited parts of the domain.

In this respect, Beven (2020) is especially relevant. The key point is not that every difficult basin must be treated as completely unique, but that some of the most informative failures may occur where local controls, data inconsistencies, or unrepresented processes matter enough that a general regional model cannot fully compensate for them. Seen in this light, the lower-skill basins are not merely residual errors; they are potential indicators of where the benchmark encounters the limits of the available information and of the current model class. Refsgaard et al. (2022) similarly emphasize that model credibility depends not only on achieving good summary performance, but also on understanding where and why similar metrics may correspond to

different underlying process realism. The difficult basins therefore deserve attention not because they undermine the benchmark, but because they expose the remaining hydrologic problem.

785 The updated diagnostics also help sharpen one important distinction: the lower-skill subset does not appear to be primarily a subset of basins with simply missing or unusable core data. The missing-data flags and core-variable completeness diagnostics do not indicate systematic absence of observed discharge, precipitation, or temperature in these basins. Instead, what distinguishes the lower-skill subset is the character of the signal itself: higher zero-flow tendency, higher precipitation-zero frequency, lower runoff efficiency, lower mean discharge, and greater year-to-year variability in runoff-related signatures. In other words, the difficulty seems to arise less from a simple lack of data and more from the fact that the available hydro-meteorological signal is sparse, intermittent, weak, or threshold-dominated. This is a scientifically important distinction because it implies that the main challenge is not only one of data availability, but one of representational adequacy for difficult regimes.

790

795

Geographic distribution of basin-wise NSE for the cluster-wise family benchmark

The six panels show local zooms colored by basin-wise seed-averaged NSE; isolated spatial outliers were excluded only from the display windows (excluded basins across clusters: n = 29).

Figure 12: Geographic distribution of basin-wise NSE for the cluster-wise family benchmark. The six panels show local zooms colored by basin-wise seed-averaged NSE. The figure highlights that lower-skill basins are not randomly scattered, but are concentrated within particular hydrologic-geographic settings, especially the drier and more water-limited parts of the study domain.

4.4. *Why skill is not uniform in time: seasonal and interannual regime shifts*

800 The new diagnostics also show that model performance is not temporally uniform. This is visible both across water years and across seasons, and the pattern is hydrologically meaningful rather than merely stochastic. In the water-year analysis, some years are systematically more difficult than others, with weaker performance concentrated especially in 1990, 1992, and 1996, 805 whereas 1997 and 1998 are comparatively favorable. These weaker years are not just globally weaker in a diffuse sense; they are also characterized by more basin-year cases with low NSE, and those cases are again disproportionately concentrated in the drier and more challenging clusters.

The hydrologic signal behind this temporal non-uniformity is consistent 810 across several diagnostics. Basin-year cases with lower skill tend to occur where runoff ratio is lower, mean flow is lower, precipitation is lower, and zero-flow or low-flow indicators are higher. Thus, lower skill in particular years does not appear to arise for arbitrary reasons; rather, it tends to lose skill when basin-year behavior moves toward dry, low-yield, intermittent, 815 and less runoff-efficient regimes. This suggests that the learned model behavior is regime-sensitive: the benchmark performs most consistently when the hydrograph remains within a domain of relatively smooth and identifiable forcing–response structure, and it becomes less stable when basin-year conditions shift into more episodic or threshold-controlled behavior.

820 A similar interpretation emerges from the seasonal diagnostics. The benchmark is strongest in JFM and AMJ, weaker in OND, and clearly most challenged in JAS. This is not just a generic “summer effect” but a hydrologically structured one. Basin-season cases with lower skill in JAS are associated

with lower runoff ratio, lower mean flow, lower baseflow index, lower snow
825 fraction, lower flow-duration-curve slope, higher aridity, higher low-flow frequency, and higher zero-flow tendency. In other words, JAS performance degradation is concentrated in basins where the warm-season hydrologic signal becomes sparse, weak, and episodic. It is therefore plausible that JAS is not difficult because it is merely a different season, but because in much
830 of the benchmark domain it pushes runoff generation into a regime where flow is small, discontinuous, and more weakly constrained by the observed meteorological inputs.

One of the most useful findings of the updated analysis is that these temporal shifts are not only visible in seasonal or annual performance summaries, but also linked to basin characteristics derived from the training data
835 themselves. Basins with larger interannual instability in model skill tend to have lower runoff efficiency and greater runoff-related variability in the training period. Similarly, basins with stronger summer difficulties tend to lack the strong seasonal organizing features seen in the most predictable snow-
840 influenced and runoff-efficient groups. These results do not prove causality, but they strengthen the interpretation that non-uniform model performance across years and seasons is related to the hydrologic variability of place, not only to random variation in training or testing.

4.5. *Implications for regional hydrological deep learning, NSE interpretation, and comparative hydrology*

845

From a data-science perspective, the results suggest that the benchmark has successfully learned strong regional response modes, but that its residual failures are concentrated where the forcing–response relationship becomes

more weakly identifiable from the available predictors. This interpretation is
850 aligned with recent work by Heudorfer et al. (2025), who argue that current
hydrologic deep-learning models may still struggle to make full use of the
information encoded in physiographic proxies, even when predictive perfor-
mance is strong in aggregate. In that light, it is not surprising that wet,
responsive, or strongly seasonal clusters are easier: the relevant streamflow
855 signal is more directly expressed in the meteorological input history. Con-
versely, in dry or threshold-dominated regimes, the unobserved internal states
and local controls may matter more, while the available static descriptors may
not yet be exploited strongly enough by the model to close that gap. Thus,
the weaker performance in Cluster 3 should not be read simply as a “bad
860 model” outcome, but as evidence about where current LSTM-style regional
frameworks still face limits in extracting and using catchment identity.

The metric pattern is also informative in this regard. Kratzert et al.
(2024) argue that the benefit of regional multi-basin training for LSTMs is
not confined to NSE alone, but is expressed across correlation-based and
865 variance-related metrics, while effects on bias-type metrics are often smaller.
This perspective helps interpret the present benchmark: the cluster structure
in NSE is likely capturing not only average agreement, but also differences in
the model’s ability to reproduce the variability and event structure of runoff
across distinct hydrologic regimes. At the same time, Gupta et al. (2009)
870 showed that NSE should not be treated as a monolithic score, because it
conflates correlation, variability, and bias components. This is one reason
why the contrasts observed here should not be over-interpreted as evidence of
a single hydrologic mechanism. Rather, they should be understood as multi-

component performance differences whose origin likely combines variability
875 reproduction, flow timing, event amplitude, and the extent to which different
runoff regimes are learnable from the available predictors.

More broadly, the present findings resonate with several themes in the
hydrologic literature. The notion that catchments occupy a continuum of
hydro-climatic gradients (Addor et al., 2017) is strongly supported here by
880 the spatial and temporal structure of skill. The caution from Refsgaard
et al. (2022) that predictive success and process adequacy are not identical
remains highly relevant. And Beven (2020)'s emphasis on the uniqueness of
the place offers a natural interpretation for the fact that a small subset of
basins remains difficult despite strong overall benchmark performance. In
885 that sense, the present study does more than provide a strong benchmark: it
also highlights where a regional deep-learning framework appears most hy-
drologically compatible with the data, and where the remaining mismatches
suggest unresolved process, state, or representation problems.

These conclusions also connect more broadly to the long-standing open
890 questions emphasized by Blöschl et al. (2019). Many of these questions re-
main fundamentally concerned with how climate, landscape structure, stor-
age, vegetation, and subsurface controls combine to produce distinct runoff
behaviors across places and time. The present benchmark does not attempt
to resolve such questions directly. However, by examining rainfall–runoff
895 prediction systematically across 531 CAMELS-US basins, it provides a large-
sample diagnostic perspective on where current regional deep-learning models
appear to perform robustly and where they remain challenged. In that sense,
the benchmark does not close those hydrologic questions, but it may help il-

luminate part of the terrain on which they still stand, especially by showing
900 that the most difficult cases are concentrated in drier, less runoff-efficient
basins with frequent low-flow or near-zero-flow conditions rather than being
randomly distributed across the domain. We therefore see this benchmark
not as an answer to those broader hydrologic questions, but as one empirical
step that may help guide where future observation, process interpretation,
905 and model development can be most informative.

Limitations and future directions. This study focuses on LSTM-based mod-
els as a strong and widely used regional benchmark, and does not include
direct comparison with more recent architectures such as Transformer-based
models, Temporal Fusion Transformers, or hybrid and physics-informed ap-
910 proaches. While the present results demonstrate that highly optimized re-
gional LSTM ensembles remain competitive and informative at continental
scale, a systematic comparison with these alternative modelling paradigms
is an important direction for future work. Such comparisons could help
determine whether the observed regime-dependent performance patterns are
915 model-specific or represent broader limitations across different classes of data-
driven hydrologic models.

4.6. Future research directions

The present benchmark points to several concrete directions for future
research.

920 First, dry and intermittent regimes deserve explicit attention as a distinct
model-development target rather than as marginal outliers. The dominant
failure mode of the benchmark is not associated with the snow-influenced or

high-yield parts of the domain, but with basins characterized by low runoff ratio, low mean discharge, high low-flow frequency, and high zero-flow ten-
925 dency. Improving prediction in such basins may require model designs that better represent threshold activation, episodic runoff generation, and strong sensitivity to antecedent state.

Second, the results suggest that richer information about catchment state and storage may be necessary. Many of the difficult basins are likely influ-
930 enced by subsurface controls, effective storage deficits, and local geological constraints that are not directly represented in standard forcing–response inputs. Future work should therefore examine whether integrating more informative static descriptors, groundwater-related proxies, remotely sensed state variables, or hybrid state-aware formulations can improve skill in low-
935 efficiency and high-intermittency regimes.

Third, the current results motivate more explicit evaluation of *temporal skill stability*. The fact that some basins show greater variation in performance across water years and seasons suggests that benchmarking should not stop at full-period performance summaries. Future studies should investigate
940 whether temporal instability in model skill is systematically associated with hydrologic signatures, basin attributes, or training-period variability metrics.

Fourth, the favorable behavior of snow-influenced basins raises an important follow-up question. It remains unclear whether their higher predictability reflects genuinely better learning of snow-related hydrologic processes,
945 or simply the presence of a more organized seasonal signal. Distinguishing between those explanations will require dedicated analysis of melt timing, recession structure, storage-release behavior, and perhaps process-oriented

evaluation beyond standard runoff metrics.

Finally, from a broader comparative-hydrology perspective, the benchmark suggests that the most scientifically informative basins may not be the average ones, but the basins that resist prediction despite strong regional training. Those lower-skill basins may encode unresolved aspects of storage, connectivity, geology, or hydroclimatic intermittency that are central to long-standing hydrologic questions. In that sense, future work should treat them not merely as exceptions, but as strategically valuable test cases for advancing both hydrologic understanding and regional deep-learning methodology.

5. Conclusions

This study presented a new highly optimized deep-learning benchmark for rainfall–runoff modelling on 531 CAMELS-US basins. Using the same basin set and train/validation/test split adopted by Kratzert et al. (2024), we combined large-scale random-search hyperparameter optimization, ensemble learning, and a cluster-wise validation-based selection strategy to develop a stronger and more hydrologically informative regional LSTM benchmark. Relative to the existing regional benchmark, both proposed optimized frameworks improved the full-hydrograph results, and the cluster-wise selected regional ensemble emerged as the strongest and most consistent overall configuration. The gain was visible not only in robust central statistics such as median NSE, but also in aggregate regional performance, indicating that the improvement extends across the basin population rather than being confined to a few isolated catchments.

A key scientific result is that benchmark skill is strongly structured by

hydrologic regime. Performance was highest in the wettest and most runoff-efficient basins and in the most snow-influenced, topographically elevated basins, whereas the weakest performance was concentrated in the driest, most
975 water-limited, and most intermittent group of basins. Only a small subset of the 531 basins fell below the diagnostic threshold of $NSE < 0.5$, and those basins were concentrated primarily in the dry and low-flow-dominated regime rather than being randomly distributed across the domain. The updated diagnostics further showed that these lower-skill basins are character-
980 ized less by simple missing-data problems than by difficult hydrologic behavior: low runoff ratio, low mean discharge, high zero-flow tendency, high low-flow frequency, and stronger seasonal and interannual instability. In this sense, the remaining lower-skill cases appear to reflect difficult hydrologic behavior rather than simple data-availability limitations.

985 The benchmark also revealed that model performance is not temporally uniform. Skill decreased in the most challenging water years and in the summer season, especially where basin behavior shifted toward dry, low-yield, and intermittent regimes. This suggests that the learned model behavior is regime-sensitive: the benchmark is strongest where the forcing–response
990 relation is more persistent, organized, and identifiable, and weaker where runoff generation becomes sparse, thresholded, or strongly conditioned by latent storage and local controls. Together, these results contribute not only a stronger regional reference model, but also a continental-scale diagnostic view of where current deep-learning rainfall–runoff models are most reliable, where
995 they remain limited, and which basin classes may offer the most informative targets for future hydrologic and methodological research.

Codes and data availability

The code developed for this study is publicly available at <https://github.com/farzadhoseini/Cluster-Wise-HPO-CAMELS-US>. The benchmark results generated during the current work are publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20421012>.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the Instituto de Hidráulica Ambiental de la Universidad de Cantabria (IHCantabria), which funded the investigation and provided the essential computational resources. The authors also gratefully acknowledge the developers of the NeuralHydrology Python library for their valuable open-source contributions. We further thank the researchers who developed and made the CAMELS-US dataset publicly available, thereby providing an essential foundation for large-sample hydrology and comparative rainfall-runoff research.

References

- Addor, N., Newman, A.J., Mizukami, N., Clark, M.P., 2017. The camels data set: catchment attributes and meteorology for large-sample studies. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 21, 5293–5313. doi:10.5194/hess-21-5293-2017.
- Bergstra, J., Bengio, Y., 2012. Random search for hyper-parameter optimization. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 13, 281–305.

- Beven, K., 2020. Deep learning, hydrological processes and the uniqueness of place. *Hydrological Processes* 34.
- 1020 Blöschl, G., et al., 2019. Twenty-three unsolved problems in hydrology (uph) – a community perspective. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 64(10), 1141–1158. doi:10.1080/02626667.2019.1620507.
- Donnelly, J., Daneshkhah, A., Abolfathi, S., 2024. Physics-informed neural networks as surrogate models of hydrodynamic simulators. *Science of the Total Environment* 912, 168814.
- 1025 Gauch, M., Kratzert, F., Klotz, D., Nearing, G., Cohen, D., Gilon, O., 2025. How to deal with missing input data. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 29, 6221–6235. doi:10.5194/hess-29-6221-2025.
- Gauch, M., et al., 2023. In defense of metrics: Metrics sufficiently encode typical human preferences regarding hydrological model performance. *Water Resources Research* 59, e2022WR033918.
- 1030 Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., Courville, A., 2016. *Deep Learning*. MIT Press. <http://www.deeplearningbook.org>.
- Gupta, H.V., Kling, H., Yilmaz, K.K., Martinez, G.F., 2009. Decomposition of the mean squared error and nse performance criteria: Implications for improving hydrological modelling. *Journal of Hydrology* 377. doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2009.08.003.
- 1035 Heudorfer, B., Gupta, H.V., Loritz, R., 2025. Are deep learning models in hydrology entity aware? *Geophysical Research Letters* 52, e2024GL113036.

- 1040 Hochreiter, S., Schmidhuber, J., 1997. Long short-term memory. *Neural Computation* 9, 1735–1780.
- Hosseini, F., Prieto, C., Álvarez, C., 2024a. Hyperparameter optimization of regional hydrological LSTMs by random search: A case study from Basque Country, Spain. *Journal of Hydrology* 643, 132003.
- 1045 Hosseini, F., Prieto, C., Álvarez, C., 2025a. Ensemble learning of catchment-wise optimized LSTMs enhances regional rainfall-runoff modelling- case study: Basque Country, Spain. *Journal of Hydrology* 646, 132269.
- Hosseini, F., Prieto, C., Álvarez, C., 2025b. An explainable AI approach for interpreting regionally optimized deep neural networks in hydrological prediction. *Journal of Hydrology* 661, 133689.
- 1050 Hosseini, F., Sierra, C.P., Álvarez, C., 2024b. Alpine-peaks shape of optimized configurations post random search in regional hydrological lstms, in: 2024 10th International Conference on Optimization and Applications (ICOA). doi:10.1109/ICOA62581.2024.10754182.
- 1055 Kratzert, F., Gauch, M., Klotz, D., Nearing, G., 2024. HESS Opinions: Never train a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network on a single basin. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 28, 4187–4201.
- Kratzert, F., Klotz, D., Brenner, C., Schulz, K., Herrnegger, M., 2018. Rainfall–runoff modelling using long short-term memory (LSTM) networks. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 22, 6005–6022.
- 1060

- Kratzert, F., et al., 2019. Towards learning universal, regional, and local hydrological behaviors via machine learning applied to large-sample datasets. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 23, 5089–5110.
- Liu, J., Bian, Y., Lawson, K., Shen, C., 2024. Probing the limit of hydrologic predictability with the transformer network. *Journal of Hydrology* 637. doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.131389.
- Nash, J., Sutcliffe, J., 1970. River flow forecasting through conceptual models part i — a discussion of principles. *Journal of Hydrology* 10. doi:10.1016/0022-1694(70)90255-6.
- Prieto, C., Kavetski, D., Le Vine, N., Álvarez, C., Medina, R., 2021. Identification of dominant hydrological mechanisms using bayesian inference, multiple statistical hypothesis testing, and flexible models. *Water Resources Research* 57.
- Prieto, C., Le Vine, N., Kavetski, D., Fenicia, F., Scheidegger, A., Vitolo, C., 2022. An exploration of bayesian identification of dominant hydrological mechanisms in ungauged catchments. *Water Resources Research* 58.
- Prieto, C., Patel, D., Han, D., 2020. Preface: Advances in flood risk assessment and management. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 20, 1045–1048. doi:10.5194/nhess-20-1045-2020.
- Refsgaard, J.C., Stisen, S., Koch, J., 2022. Hydrological process knowledge in catchment modelling – lessons and perspectives from 60 years development. *Hydrological Processes* 36, e14463. doi:10.1002/hyp.14463.

Shen, C., Lawson, K., 2021. Applications of deep learning in hydrology. Deep Learning for the Earth Sciences: A Comprehensive Approach to Remote Sensing, Climate Science, and Geosciences , 283–297.

Surowiecki, J., 2004. The Wisdom of Crowds: Why the Many Are Smarter Than the Few and How Collective Wisdom Shapes Business, Economics, Societies and Nations. Doubleday, New York, NY, USA.

Tripathy, K.P., Mishra, A.K., 2024. Deep learning in hydrology and water resources disciplines: concepts, methods, applications, and research directions. Journal of Hydrology 628, 130458.

Xie, K., et al., 2021. Physics-guided deep learning for rainfall-runoff modeling by considering extreme events and monotonic relationships. Journal of Hydrology 603, 127043.

CAMELS-US study basins grouped into six hydrologically informed clusters

Hydrological signatures across the six clusters

Hydro-climatic profile of each cluster

(values in cells = raw cluster medians; colors = standardized anomalies)

Distribution of basin-wise test-period NSE across the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Model	N	Mean	Median	Q25	Q75
Benchmark	531	0.753	0.792	0.721	0.844
Cluster-wise	531	0.776	0.815	0.745	0.864
Top10	531	0.769	0.812	0.738	0.864

ECDF of basin-wise test-period NSE across the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Benchmark: low=33, accepted=498 (N=531) | Cluster-wise: low=30, accepted=501 (N=531) | Top10: low=30, accepted=501 (N=531)

Low performance: < 0.5

Accepted performance: ≥ 0.5

Water-year evolution of median basin-wise NSE across the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Heatmap of median basin-wise NSE by water year and benchmark framework

Yearly distributions of basin-wise NSE

Cluster-wise family ensemble

Top-10 family ensemble

Reference benchmark

Seasonal heatmap of median basin-wise NSE across water years for the cluster-wise family benchmark

Model	JFM	AMJ	JAS	OND	Overall
Cluster-wise	0.744	0.760	0.494	0.644	0.660

Cluster-level summary of basin-wise NSE for the three benchmark frameworks

NSE median

NSE mean

NSE minimum

NSE maximum

Geographic distribution of the lower-skill basins in the cluster-wise family benchmark

Basins with $NSE < 0.5$ are highlighted; the remaining CAMELS-US basins are shown in gray

Geographic distribution of basin-wise NSE for the cluster-wise family benchmark

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2
Sample	n = 83	n = 195
Median NSE	median = 0.761	median = 0.818
Mean NSE	mean = 0.732	mean = 0.801

Cluster 1

Cluster 2

	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Sample	n = 67	n = 61
Median NSE	median = 0.684	median = 0.881
Mean NSE	mean = 0.598	mean = 0.879

Cluster 3

Cluster 4

	Cluster 5	Cluster 6
Sample	n = 66	n = 59
Median NSE	median = 0.872	median = 0.775
Mean NSE	mean = 0.857	mean = 0.760

Cluster 5

Cluster 6

Climatic and topographic gradients across the six clusters

Attribute-space separation of the six clusters

Composition of each cluster by USGS 2-digit hydrologic region (HUC-02)

Basins with NSE < threshold vs remaining basins

Counts of basin-year cases with NSE < threshold in weaker water years

Lower-skill basin-year cases in weaker water years vs remaining basin-year cases

Counts of basin-season cases with NSE < 0.5 by season and cluster

Number of lower-skill basin-season cases

JAS basin-season cases with NSE < threshold vs remaining basin-season cases

Hydro-climatic signature of basins with pronounced JAS performance loss

Cluster-wise model: median basin-wise NSE by water year

Distribution of seed-level NSE values after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Model	N	Mean	Median	Q25	Q75
Benchmark	10	0.753	0.754	0.751	0.755
Cluster-wise	10	0.776	0.776	0.776	0.777
Top10	10	0.769	0.770	0.768	0.770

CDF of seed-level NSE values after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

	Benchmark	Cluster-wise		Top10	
Model	N	Mean	Median	Q25	Q75
Benchmark	10	0.220	0.251	0.169	0.340
Cluster-wise	10	0.606	0.605	0.599	0.616
Top10	10	0.385	0.377	0.336	0.419

CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

	Benchmark	Cluster-wise	Top10		
Model	N	Mean	Median	Q25	Q75
Benchmark	10	0.734	0.735	0.730	0.743
Cluster-wise	10	0.783	0.783	0.782	0.784
Top10	10	0.775	0.774	0.772	0.777

CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Table 1

Distributional summary of selected climatic, physiographic, and hydrologic attributes for the 531 CAMELS-US basins used in this study. Q5 and Q95 denote the 5th and 95th percentiles, respectively.

Source: main.tex

Attribute	Unit	Q5	Mean	Median	Q95
Catchment area	km ²	23.26	494.99	337.19	1581.39
Mean elevation	m	64.24	737.05	437.01	2656.98
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	1.54	3.41	3.27	6.49
Aridity index	-	0.34	0.98	0.85	2.03
Snow fraction	-	0.002	0.172	0.090	0.675
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.12	1.61	1.17	5.48
Runoff ratio	-	0.08	0.41	0.36	0.90
Baseflow index	-	0.18	0.49	0.50	0.72
Flow-duration-curve slope	-	0.34	1.26	1.30	2.01
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	1.45	23.48	15.20	65.43
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.70	106.37	97.15	254.14
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.13

Table 2

Hydro-climatic summary of the six CAMELS-US clusters used in the cluster-wise regional modelling framework. Rep

Source: main.tex

Cluster	n	P	Aridity	Snow frac.	Q
1	83	2.77	0.90	0.08	0.79
2	195	3.50	0.73	0.10	1.48
3	67	1.83	1.75	0.02	0.21
4	61	6.29	0.36	0.14	5.36
5	66	2.41	1.38	0.66	1.23
6	59	3.68	0.87	0.00	1.05

P: mean precipitation [mm d^{-1}]; Snow frac.: fraction of precipitation falling as snow; Q: mean discharge [mm d^{-1}]; BFI: baseflow index; Aridity: the ratio of potential evapotranspiration to precipitation.

Sorted values are cluster medians.

Runoff ratio	BFI	Low-flow freq.
0.28	0.31	179.20
0.42	0.51	75.25
0.11	0.35	212.40
0.78	0.55	96.85
0.53	0.61	76.05
0.30	0.49	85.15

flow index; Low-flow freq.: low-flow frequency. Aridity is defined as

Hyperparameter search space explored in this study, the values represented among the selected configurations are those adopted from the reference setup.

Source: main.tex

Hyperparameter	Full HPO search space
Sequence length L [days]	90, 120, 180, 270, 360, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1095, 1460, 1825
Hidden size	16, 32, 64, 128, 256
Initial forget-gate bias	-3, -1, 0, 1, 3, 5
Output dropout	0, 0.2, 0.4
Batch size	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
Learning rate at epoch 0 (Lr0)	10^{-3} , 10^{-2}
Learning rate at epoch 10 (Lr10)	5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3} , 5×10^{-3}
Learning rate at epoch 25 (Lr25)	10^{-4} , 10^{-3}
Target-noise standard deviation	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1
Loss function	NSE, RMSE
Number of retained configurations	

Table 3

ed Top-10 regional configurations, the values represented among the selected cluster-wise configurations, c

Selected Top-10 regional family	Selected cluster-wise family
90, 365, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1460	270, 365, 450, 540, 730, 900, 1460, 1825
64, 128, 256	128, 256
-3, -1, 1, 3, 5	-3, -1, 0, 1, 3, 5
0, 0.2, 0.4	0, 0.2, 0.4
32, 64, 128, 256, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
10^{-3}	10^{-3}
5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	5×10^{-4} , 10^{-3}
10^{-4} , 10^{-3}	10^{-4} , 10^{-3}
0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1
NSE, RMSE	NSE, RMSE
10 regional configs	18 configs (top 3 per cluster)

and the fixed regional benchmark configuration

Regional benchmark Kratzert_2024

365

256

3

0.4

256

10^{-3}

5×10^{-4}

10^{-4}

0

NSE

single fixed setup

Preprint not peer reviewed

Table 4

Comparison of the three benchmark frameworks over the full test-period hydrograph. For each framework, both the median and the mean are included as the primary robust summary, while the mean is included to reflect aggregate regional performance across the full test-period.

Source: main.tex

Framework	Summary	NSE	KGE	Pearson-r
Benchmark (Kratzert et al., 2024)	Median	0.79	0.79	0.90
Benchmark (Kratzert et al., 2024)	Mean	0.75	0.74	0.88
Top-10 family ensemble	Median	0.81	0.77	0.91
Top-10 family ensemble	Mean	0.77	0.73	0.90
Cluster-wise family ensemble	Median	0.82	0.79	0.92
Cluster-wise family ensemble	Mean	0.78	0.74	0.90

Bold values in the manuscript indicate the best result within each summary type. Higher is better for NSE, KGE, and Pearson-r; lower is better for Peak-MAPE; Peak time is days; Peak-MAPE is %.

Median and mean across the 531 basins are reported. The median is shown for the basin population.

RMSE	Peak time	Peak-MAPE	Missed peaks
1.13	0.27	35.22	0.35
1.32	0.39	38.45	0.38
1.06	0.24	34.86	0.33
1.25	0.37	37.53	0.37
1.06	0.25	34.36	0.33
1.25	0.36	37.21	0.36

Lower is better for RMSE, peak time, Peak-MAPE, and missed peaks. RMSE is mm d^{-1} ;

Table 5

Median basin-wise NSE by water year for the three benchmark frameworks, computed from seed-averaged best-performing framework in each water year. The last two rows summarize the average yearly per each framework ranks first.

Source: main.tex

Water year	Benchmark	Cluster-wise
1990	0.768	0.789
1991	0.784	0.808
1992	0.757	0.804
1993	0.804	0.827
1994	0.790	0.822
1995	0.793	0.826
1996	0.764	0.788
1997	0.810	0.838
1998	0.826	0.850
1999	0.785	0.818
Mean over water years	0.788	0.817
Years ranked first	0	8

averaged predictions. Bold values indicate the performance and the number of years in which

Top-10

0.786
0.802
0.789
0.828
0.818
0.821
0.790
0.832
0.847
0.816
0.813
2

Preprint not peer reviewed

Table 6

Seasonal median NSE summarized across water years for the three benchmark frameworks. Bold values indicate the best-performing framework within each season. The final column reports the mean of the four seasonal summaries for each framework.

Source: main.tex

Framework	JFM	AMJ	JAS	OND	Overall
Benchmark	0.685	0.696	0.368	0.565	0.579
Top-10 family	0.737	0.751	0.488	0.634	0.652
Cluster-wise family	0.745	0.761	0.494	0.644	0.661

JFM: January–March; AMJ: April–June; JAS: July–September; OND: October–December.

Table 7

Cluster-wise family ensemble: cluster-level summary of basin-wise NSE. Reported values are computed across basins within each hydrologically coherent cluster after seed-averaging at basin level.

Source: main.tex

Statistic	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
Median	0.761	0.818	0.684	0.881	0.872	0.775
Mean	0.732	0.801	0.598	0.879	0.857	0.760
Q25	0.591	0.696	0.464	0.834	0.819	0.636
Q75	0.888	0.923	0.826	0.923	0.931	0.858
Minimum	0.170	0.398	-0.346	0.765	0.417	0.518
Maximum	0.913	0.918	0.891	0.960	0.963	0.903

Table 8

Summary of performance-defined benchmark subsets for the cluster-wise family. The NSE <0.5 subset is used as a diagnostic threshold subset in the discussion, not as a categorical claim about model adequacy.

Source: main.tex

Subset definition	Number of basins	Share of benchmark (%)
NSE < 0.5	30	5.65
NSE ≥ 0.6	478	90.02
NSE ≥ 0.7	437	82.30
NSE ≥ 0.8	300	56.50
NSE ≥ 0.9	53	9.98

The NSE < 0.5 subset is used as a diagnostic threshold subset, not as a categorical claim about model adequacy.

Table 9

Cluster-wise distribution of lower-skill basins using two diagnostic thresholds in the cluster-wise family benchmark. Percent relative to the number of basins in each cluster.

Source: main.tex

Cluster	n basins	n with NSE <0.5	Share (%)	n with NSE <0.7
C1	83	6	7.2	22
C2	195	2	1.0	20
C3	67	21	31.3	36
C4	61	0	0.0	0
C5	66	1	1.5	2
C6	59	0	0.0	14

Preprint not peer reviewed

Table S1

Overall hydro-climatic summary statistics for the 531 CAMELS-US basins used in this study. The table reports descriptive statistics joining the CAMELS-US attribute files with the 531-basin cluster-assignment file. Q5 and Q95 denote the 5th and 95th percentiles.

Source: supplementary.tex

Attribute	Unit	Q5	Mean	SD	Q95
Catchment area	km ²	22	477	473	126
Mean elevation	m	56	728	788	249
Mean slope	m km ⁻¹	3.2	46.2	47.3	7.4
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	1.51	3.39	1.37	2.57
Potential evapotranspiration	mm d ⁻¹	2.08	2.77	0.54	2.32
Aridity index	-	0.34	0.97	0.51	0.68
Snow fraction	-	0.00	0.17	0.20	0.04
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.10	1.60	1.55	0.76
Runoff ratio	-	0.06	0.41	0.23	0.26
Baseflow index	-	0.18	0.48	0.16	0.40
Flow-duration-curve slope	-	0.34	1.27	0.50	0.94
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	1.5	23.9	26.0	6.2
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.6	107.4	79.5	41.3
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00	0.03	0.10	0.00

istics across the full benchmark sample after ntiles, respectively.

Median	Q75	Q95
310	693	1563
437	823	2679
29.0	72.6	139.8
3.27	3.82	6.49
2.66	3.13	3.79
0.84	1.10	2.03
0.10	0.22	0.69
1.18	1.82	5.48
0.36	0.53	0.88
0.50	0.59	0.72
1.31	1.65	2.01
14.6	35.5	68.5
97.5	160.5	255.2
0.00	0.00	0.14

Preprint not peer reviewed

Cluster-wise hydro-climatic summary statistics for the six CAMELS-US clusters. Values are reported as median [Q25-

Source: supplementary.tex

Attribute	Unit	C1
Catchment area	km ²	568 [249-944]
Mean elevation	m	292 [229-375]
Mean slope	m km ⁻¹	6.4 [4.0-8.7]
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	2.77 [2.60-3.21]
Potential evapotranspiration	mm d ⁻¹	2.58 [2.44-2.72]
Aridity index	-	0.90 [0.85-1.02]
Snow fraction	-	0.08 [0.06-0.10]
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.79 [0.58-0.98]
Runoff ratio	-	0.28 [0.22-0.32]
Baseflow index	-	0.31 [0.23-0.42]
Flow-duration-curve slope	-	0.92 [0.72-1.30]
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	35.6 [18.4-45.5]
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	179.2 [127.4-207.0]
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00 [0.00-0.03]

Table S2

Q75] across basins within each cluster. This table provides a more detailed numerical cha

C2	C3
246 [121-520]	436 [192-893]
418 [263-597]	684 [447-1137]
33.0 [14.1-52.2]	20.8 [9.9-60.7]
3.50 [3.21-3.88]	1.83 [1.36-2.40]
2.55 [2.27-2.86]	3.37 [2.96-3.53]
0.73 [0.64-0.82]	1.75 [1.48-2.18]
0.10 [0.04-0.20]	0.02 [0.00-0.16]
1.48 [1.10-1.88]	0.21 [0.07-0.38]
0.42 [0.34-0.50]	0.11 [0.05-0.17]
0.51 [0.44-0.57]	0.35 [0.18-0.52]
1.51 [1.29-1.73]	0.53 [0.22-1.06]
8.8 [5.4-15.6]	36.4 [16.7-77.6]
75.2 [36.9-106.6]	212.4 [105.6-274.2]
0.00 [0.00-0.00]	0.04 [0.00-0.24]

Characterization of the cluster contrasts summarized in the main manuscript.

C4	C5
229 [79-526]	175 [47-431]
728 [486-922]	2484 [2050-3003]
112.1 [90.3-126.7]	106.5 [84.2-137.3]
6.29 [5.09-7.21]	2.41 [1.81-2.84]
2.17 [2.06-2.43]	3.00 [2.69-3.33]
0.36 [0.29-0.48]	1.38 [1.01-1.60]
0.14 [0.05-0.32]	0.66 [0.49-0.71]
5.36 [3.58-6.26]	1.23 [0.68-1.74]
0.78 [0.65-0.95]	0.53 [0.33-0.66]
0.55 [0.51-0.60]	0.61 [0.53-0.65]
1.80 [1.55-2.02]	0.96 [0.77-1.27]
8.2 [3.2-16.8]	29.0 [13.1-47.4]
96.8 [47.5-131.4]	76.1 [12.5-151.8]
0.00 [0.00-0.00]	0.00 [0.00-0.00]

c6

364 [133-864]
71 [35-127]
5.0 [2.6-7.4]
3.68 [3.32-3.96]
3.19 [2.64-3.61]
0.87 [0.81-0.97]
0.00 [0.00-0.05]
1.05 [0.87-1.30]
0.30 [0.25-0.37]
0.49 [0.41-0.62]
1.30 [0.99-1.58]
13.6 [2.8-28.6]
85.2 [14.1-140.5]
0.00 [0.00-0.00]

Preprint not peer reviewed

Dominant categorical characteristics of each cluster, including the most frequent geology class. Percentages are computed relative to the number of basins in each cluster.

Source: supplementary.tex

Cluster	n	Dominant geology class
C1	83	Carbonate sedimentary rocks (39.8%)
C2	195	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (50.8%)
C3	67	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (29.9%)
C4	61	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (39.3%)
C5	66	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (25.8%)
C6	59	Unconsolidated sediments (67.8%)

Table S3

ology class, dominant land-cover type, and principal USGS 2-digit hydrologic region (HUC-02) contributions.

Dominant land-cover type	Main HUC-02 contributions
Croplands (50.6%)	10 MISSOURI (31.3%); 07 Upper Mississippi (31.3%); 03 Ohio (13.3%)
Deciduous Broadleaf Forest (51.3%)	02 MID-ATLANTIC (27.7%); 03 SOUTH ATLANTIC-Gulf (23.1%); 03 Ohio (12.3%)
Grasslands (41.8%)	12 Texas-Gulf (30.0%); 15 LOWER COLORADO (17.4%); 10 CALIFORNIA (16.4%)
Evergreen Needleleaf Forest (90.2%)	17 PACIFIC NORTHWEST (80.3%); 10 CALIFORNIA (7.0%); 01 NEW England (1.6%)
Grasslands (48.5%)	17 PACIFIC NORTHWEST (23.0%); 10 MISSOURI (21.2%); 14 Upper Colorado (21.2%)
Woody Savannas (47.5%)	03 SOUTH ATLANTIC-Gulf (22.7%); 04 Great Lakes (13.3%); 02 MID-Atlantic (11.9%)